

Dielectric Barrier Discharge Ionization with different sample introduction formats for small molecule applications

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Abstract:

Dielectric barrier discharges (DBD) are used as soft ionization sources for mass spectrometers (MS) or ion mobility spectrometers, enabling excellent possibilities for analytical applications. Detailed studies have increased knowledge about fundamental discharge mechanisms in noble gas discharges at atmospheric pressure, which have led to further improvements in the use of these discharges. The present communication describes different sample introduction formats using DBD based-devices as ionization tools. These devices configurations are: dielectric barrier discharge ionization, low-temperature plasma and flexible micro-tube plasma. Those devices were compared with more conventional sample introduction interfaces, such as electrospray, paper spray or atmospheric pressure chemical ionization.

In order to obtain a stronger knowledge concerning the sample introduction and the role of DBD-bases plasmas, ambient-MD and gas and liquid chromatography-MS have been subjected to study.

Several and interesting research have been developed in each instrumentation.

The first one consists in the evaluation of different soft ionization devices for the direct description of wine profile by ambient- MS.

Because of the controlled atmosphere, the influence of the surrounding atmosphere can be neglected, leading to less matrix effects in the measurement. With this assumption, a sensitive and non-fragmenting ionization method was developed for determination of volatile biomarkers by gas chromatography-MS.

The last application involves the understanding of plasma when the sample introduction is a liquid. For this experiment, a multiclass detection of explosives and related compounds by liquid chromatography-MS was carried out.